

Screening for resistance to leaf spot

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Nine of 74 selected lines planted in a nursery at Rembang, Central Java, were resistant to brown spot *Helminthosporium oryzae* and stackburn *Alternaria padwickii*. These were Siam 1019, IR2071-105-4, IR2071-588-6, IR2031-254-2-3, IR2055-219-1-3, RP 633-680-1-1-1-1, ARC 5793, Balop Merah 910, and Madura Samba.

Lines resistant to narrow brown leaf spot, *Cercospora oryzae*

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Thirty-two lines from the local collection and 23 lines from the Observational

Yield Trial and from local collection found to be resistant to narrow brown leaf spot. Sukamandi, Indonesia

Observational Yield Trial	Local collection
IR796 C-MR-143-24	S. Hitam Segon
IR1514 A-5597-2	Tarak Karo
IR1909-1-3-3	Puy
IR2031-354-2-3	Tambu
IR2031-422-3-3	Paya Bokot
IR2070-78-2-3	Munte
IR2070-178-2-3	Puket Garu
IR2070-381-1-5-8	Kasih Beranak
IR2070-652-5-4-11	Gadis Kebalsi
IR2070-939-3-4-10	Rendah Renumi
IR2071-105-9-4	Umbang Katib
IR2071-573-3-3-14	Rampone
IR2071-588-3-5	S. Buyung
IR2078-71-2	Saeful Putih
IR2688-43-4-3	Lakaton Abang
IR2798-88-3	Gadabung Gundill
Si 01 b-218-3	Siem Ganol
B 1990	Laketu Mangan
b-MR-43467-3B	Pakui
B 1990	Sipanci
b-MR-43534-2B	R. Jawa
B 1990	Disi
b-MR-43534-2B	Raden Rata
B 2360-6-4-5	Bakaton Panas
B 2360-8-4-5	Lakaton Karamunting
B 2932-2-1-4-1-3	Isip
	Karang Dukuh
	Minai

Yield Trial were selected at Sukamandi, West Java, for resistance to narrow brown leaf spot *Cercospora oryzae* (see table). The new IRRI releases — PB26, PB28, PB30, PB32, and PB34 — were all rated highly susceptible to narrow brown leaf spot.

Reaction of some gall midge crosses to false smut at Mandya, Karnataka, India

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In kharif 1975, a heavy incidence of false smut *Ustilagoidea virens* was recorded on the F₃ progeny of some crosses made for gall midge at the V.C. Farm, Mandya. The disease symptoms were characterized by transformation of the paddy grains to greenish-black spore balls (smut balls) of velvety appearance. The glumes of the spikelets can still be seen on the spore masses. The disease incidence was severe enough to distinguish susceptible crosses and

susceptible F₃ lines within crosses. The plants within each progeny showing false smut were counted and recorded for all crosses. Analyses of these data are based on the rating scale system suggested in the "Standard Evaluation Systems for Rice" published by IRRI, 1975.

C2 had an incidence of less than 5 percent and was hence, moderately resistant to false smut (Table 1). C1 and C3 had less than 25 percent incidence. C4 recorded an incidence of 41.8 percent, and shall be considered susceptible.

The number of F₃ progeny in each cross has been grouped according to the percent incidence of false smut (Table 2).

No F₃ line showed a resistant reaction to false smut. However, some progeny with moderate levels of resistance (1–5% incidence) were recovered in C1 and C2. Most of the F₃ progeny exhibited from 6 to 25 percent disease incidence. In the cross C4, 2 out of 15 F₃ lines studied recorded disease incidence that exceeded 50 percent, and hence were classified as very susceptible.

Table 1. Incidence of false smut disease (*U. virens*) in progeny of crosses made for gall midge resistance. University of Agricultural Sciences, Hebbal Campus, Bangalore, Karnataka state, India.

Line	Parents	F ₃ lines (no.)	Plants within each F ₃ line (no.)	Total plants (%)	Incidence (%)
C1	Jaya/W1263	67	80	5360	11.4
C2	W1263/W12787	7	66	462	3.7
C3	Sona/W1263	10	84	840	16.6
C4	Vijaya/W12787	15	84	1260	41.8
Total		99	—	7922	18.4

Table 2. The number of F₃ progeny from crosses for gall midge resistance. University of Agricultural Sciences, Hebbal campus, Bangalore, Karnataka state, India.

Incidence (%)	Classification	Frequency of F ₃ progeny (no.)				Total (no.)	Frequency (%)
		C1	C2	C3	C4		
0– 1	R	—	—	—	—	—	—
1– 5	MR	12	5	0	0	17	17.2
6–25	HR	46	2	9	3	60	60.6
26–50	S	9	0	1	10	20	20.2
> 50	vs	—	—	—	2	2	2.0
F ₃ total no.		67	7	10	15	99	100.0